

Unraveling Key Hub Genes of Rheumatoid Arthritis Using Integrated Bioinformatics Approaches

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Abstract

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disorder characterized by persistent synovial inflammation, progressive cartilage degradation and bone erosion, resulting in significant joint dysfunction and disability. The pathogenic mechanism of RA involves interactions between immune cells, stromal cells, and cytokine networks; however, the molecular process that sustains chronic inflammation and joint damage remains incompletely characterized. In this study, an integrated bioinformatics approach was implemented to identify key genes associated with RA pathogenesis. Gene expression data from GEO datasets GSE1919 and GSE55457 were retrieved, and differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified using GEO2R online tool. Overlapping DEGs were determined using Venny 2.1 and Protein-Protein Interaction (PPI) networks were constructed using STRING and analyzed with the MCODE plugin in Cytoscape to identify biologically significant hub gene clusters. Gene ontology and pathway enrichment analysis were performed using ShinyGO, while gene expression validation was performed using the Rheumatoid Arthritis Bioinformatics Center (RABC). Together, these findings demonstrate that interferon-STAT1 pathways and T-cell kinase networks collectively contribute to the development and maintenance of RA. This integrative analysis provides novel insights into the molecular mechanisms underlying RA and highlights potential biomarkers and therapeutic candidates for future translational applications.

Keywords— Differentially Expressed Genes, Synovial Inflammation, Hub genes, Protein- Protein Interaction Network, Gene Ontology Enrichment

I. INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disease, characterized by persistent synovial joint inflammation leading to progressive cartilage and bone destruction [1], [2]. It is recognized as the most widespread form of inflammatory polyarthritis, with a worldwide adult prevalence of 0.5%-1% [3]. The clinical features of RA vary from mild joint inflammation to severe deforming symmetrical polyarthritis that causes irreversible disability [4]. RA most commonly develops between the age of 40 and 70 in women and occurs 2 to 3 times more often than men [5].

The etiology of RA is driven by multifactorial contributors involving both genetic and environmental interactions. The studies reveal that the heritability of RA is approximately 50% in anti-citrullinated protein antibody (ACPA) positive cases [6]. Among genetic determinants HLA class II histocompatibility antigen-DRB1 beta chain (HLA-DRB1) shared epitope (SE) remains the predominant contributor to RA susceptibility [7]. In addition to HLA related risk, Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 22 (PTPN22), Cytotoxic T-lymphocyte protein 4 (CTLA4), and Signal transducer and activator of transcription 4 (STAT4) have also been identified as contributing factors in disease susceptibility [8]. Environmental factors such as cigarette smoking, silica exposure, and air pollution synergize with genetic susceptibility to promote loss of immune tolerance and onset of RA [9], [10].

The autoimmune nature of RA is characterized by the production of autoantibodies, particularly rheumatoid factor (RF) and ACPA, which often precede the onset of clinical symptoms by years [11]. Dysregulated post-translational modifications (PTMs), such as citrullination and carbamylation, generate neoantigens that trigger aberrant immune activation [12]. Epigenetic mechanisms, including DNA methylation, histone modification, and microRNAs (miRNAs), further modulate gene expression and inflammatory pathways, contributing to disease persistence and progression [13].

The diagnosis of RA is established through a combined assessment of clinical, serological, and imaging findings. The current diagnostic and classification approaches for RA still rely on the 2010 American College of Rheumatology/European League Against Rheumatism (ACR/EULAR) classification criteria, which continue to serve as the foundation for diagnosing and classifying RA, incorporating joint involvement, serological markers, and acute-phase reactants [14]. Early administration of conventional synthetic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (csDMARDs), especially drugs like methotrexate, significantly limit progressive joint damage and reduce long term disability [15].

The cellular basis of RA pathogenesis is mediated by a complex network of immune and stromal cell interactions within the synovium. Pro-inflammatory cytokines such as Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), Interleukin-1 (IL-1 β), and Interleukin-6 (IL-6) are produced by activated macrophages, T cells, B cells, and fibroblasts like synoviocytes (FLS), thereby sustaining chronic inflammation and promoting joint destruction [16]. IL-6 mediated signaling represents a key pathogenic axis in RA, and dysregulation of classical versus trans-signaling contributes significantly to inflammatory activity [17]. FLS contributes to cartilage and bone destruction by secreting matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) and promoting osteoclastogenesis through Receptor Activator of Nuclear Factor kappa-B Ligand (RANKL) expression. Metabolic dysregulation involving impaired AMP-activated protein kinase and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (AMPK and PPAR- γ) signaling pathways play a crucial role in enhancing synovial hyperplasia in RA [18], [19]. Additionally, upregulation of key cell cycle regulators such as Cyclin-dependent kinase 1 (CDK1), Kinesin-like protein KIF11 (KIF11), and Cell division cycle protein 20

homolog (CDC20) promotes FLS proliferation and pannus formation [20]. The Janus kinase (JAK)/STAT pathway constitutes a central intracellular signaling cascade linking cytokine signaling to gene transcriptional activation and serves as a major therapeutic target in current RA treatment strategies [21], [22].

In this study, three GEO microarray datasets were analyzed to retrieve differently expressed genes (DEGs) in normal and RA samples. Protein-protein interaction (PPI) followed by gene ontology and pathway enrichment analysis were employed to identify targets in RA. Gene expression for the identified targets were examined to determine the key targets for targeting RA.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. GEO2R Analysis

Gene expression data was obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) database, a public data repository for functional genomics data (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>). The datasets with the accession number GSE1919 and GSE55457 were analyzed using the tool GEO2R to retrieve their DEGs. The results were downloaded to identify the top up regulated and down regulated genes. The genes exhibiting an adjusted p-value < 0.05 and $|\log_2FC| > 1$ were selected as top DEGs [23].

B. Selection of DEGs

Venn diagram was constructed using Venny 2.1, an online tool for comparing lists to identify the top DEGs from the two datasets (<https://bioinfogp.cnb.csic.es/tools/venny/>). The Venn diagrams were constructed separately to identify the common genes from top up regulated and down regulated gene sets [24].

C. PPI

The PPI network of the DEGs was constructed using the Search Tool for the Retrieval of Interacting Genes (<https://string-db.org/>). The network was downloaded and visualized using Cytoscape for further analysis using molecular complex detection (MCODE) plugin to identify clusters with higher biological relevance. MCODE was executed with parameters set to degree cutoff of 2, haircut cluster finding, node score cutoff of 0.2, K-core of 2 and maximum depth of 100 [25], [26].

D. Gene Ontology and KEGG Pathway Enrichment

The gene ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis were performed using ShinyGO, an online gene set enrichment tool (<https://bioinformatics.sdstate.edu/go/>), an interactive web-based tool for functional enrichment analysis. The results were visualized as lollipop charts. False discovery rate cutoff was set < 0.05 for demonstrating significance [27].

E. Gene Expression Analysis

Gene expression profiles for the identified RA target were obtained from Rheumatoid arthritis bioinformatics center (RABC) (<http://www.onethird-lab.com/RABC/>). The database aggregates multi-omics datasets from publicly available repositories. The expression between normal and RA cohorts was visualized in box plots. Statistical significance was evaluated through RABC differential expression module with $p < 0.05$ as significance [28].

III. RESULTS

A. Retrieval of DEGs

Fig. 1 A and B Volcano plot for DEGs retrieved from GEO datasets GSE1919 and GSE55457 through GEO2R analysis. C and D Venn diagram constructed with Venny 2.0 for up regulated and down regulated gene sets.

The datasets with accession numbers GSE1919 and GSE55457 were obtained from Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) database to retrieve DEGs related to RA by performing GEO2R analysis. The top up-regulated and down-regulated genes were identified, and volcano plots were generated through GEO2R analysis are presented in Fig 1A and 1B.

To identify common genes between the top up regulated and down regulated gene sets obtained from the two datasets, a Venn diagram was constructed. The analysis identified 28 common up-regulated genes and 75 common down-regulated genes between the selected datasets and the corresponding Venn diagrams are shown in Fig1C and Fig1D.

B. PPI Network Analysis

Fig. 2 A. PPI network obtained from STRING. B. MCODE cluster with highest score.

STRING was utilized to construct a PPI network of the top DEGs. Fig 2A represents the PPI network obtained from STRING and visualized using cytoscape for advanced analysis. MCODE plugin was utilized to identify the most significant functional cluster within the network, which demonstrates higher biological relevance, indicating strong interconnectivity among clustered genes. The cluster identified is presented in Fig 2B. The genes identified in the cluster with high score were SH2 domain-containing protein 1A (SH2D1A), Interleukin-32 (IL32), T-cell surface glycoprotein CD3 delta chain (CD3D), Protein NKG7 (NKG7), B-cell antigen receptor complex-associated protein alpha chain (CD79A), Cytokine receptor common subunit gamma (IL2RG), Protein tyrosine phosphatase receptor type C-associated protein (PTPRCAP), Granzyme B(G,H) (GZMB), T-cell surface antigen CD2 (CD2), C-C motif chemokine 5 (CCL5), Granzyme K (GZMK), Tyrosine-protein kinase Lck (LCK), T-cell surface glycoprotein CD8 alpha

chain (CD8A), C-X-C motif chemokine 13 (CXCL13), T-cell surface glycoprotein CD3 zeta chain (CD247), C-C chemokine receptor type 2 (CCR2), C-X-C motif chemokine 9 (CXCL9), Granzyme A (GZMA), Interleukin-7 receptor subunit alpha (IL7R), Signal transducer and activator of transcription 1 (STAT1), CD27 antigen (CD27), Tyrosine-protein kinase ITK/TSK (ITK), CD48 antigen CD48, and CAMPATH-1 antigen (CD52).

C. Gene Ontology and KEGG Pathway Enrichment

Gene Ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis was performed to understand the biological processes, cellular components, molecular functions and signaling pathways associated with the top DEGs. The false discovery rate (FDR) cutoff was set to < 0.05 to confirm significance. Table 1 shows the pathway and their genes that are associated with RA. The results of the enrichment analysis were visualized with lollipop charts and presented in Fig 3.

Fig. 3 Lollipop chart for gene ontology and KEGG pathway enrichment analysis. A. Biological processes B. Cellular components C. Molecular functions D. KEGG pathway enrichment

TABLE 1. THE MAIN PATHWAYS IDENTIFIED IN KEGG PATHWAY ENRICHMENT LINKED TO CAUSE RA

Path ID	Pathway	Genes
hsa04060	Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	CXCL13, IL2RG, IL7R, CXCL9, CCL5, CCR2, IL32, CD27
hsa04062	Chemokine signaling pathway	CXCL13, ITK, CXCL9, CCL5, STAT1, CCR2
hsa04659	Th17 cell differentiation	IL2RG, LCK, STAT1, CD3D, CD247
hsa04660	T cell receptor signaling pathway	ITK, LCK, CD3D, CD247, CD8A
hsa04630	JAK-STAT signaling pathway	IL2RG, IL7R, STAT1
hsa04380	Osteoclast differentiation	LCK, STAT1
hsa04620	Toll-like receptor signaling pathway	CXCL9, CCL5, STAT1

D. Gene Expression Analysis

Fig. 4 Gene expression in normal and RA samples visualized with box plot generated by RABC. A. CXCL9 B. CD3D C. IL2RG D. CXCL13 E. CD27 F. STAT1 G. LCK H. ITK I. CD247 J. IL32

Gene expression profiles for the identified RA targets were obtained from the RABC, a database that aggregates multi-omics datasets from public repositories. The differential expression between normal and RA cohorts was visualized using box plots for genes— CCL5, CCR2, CD3D, CD8A, CD27, CD247, CXCL9, CXCL13, IL2RG, IL7R, IL32, ITK, LCK, and STAT1. The plots for CCL5, CCR2, and IL7R showed no significance between the groups. IL21R is most expressed and more significant than the other targets. IL2R, CXCL13 and CXCL9 show high expression and significance while ITK, LCK, CD30, CD27, CD247 and

STAT1 are all significant but showed lower expression. The expression analysis is visualized with box plots and is presented in Fig 4.

IV. DISCUSSION

This study utilized an integrated bioinformatics approach to systematically identify DEGs, construct molecular interaction network and analyze functional enrichment and expression of potential therapeutic targets in RA. By choosing two GEO datasets, DEGs were found using GEO2R analysis method. STRING analysis has been used to construct a PPI network and MCODE has been used for module detection. Followed by enrichment analysis through GO and KEGG with ShinyGO and gene expression for validating and identifying key targets. This integrated bioinformatics approach produced a refined list of hub genes which has significant relevance to RA pathogenesis and therapeutic targeting of RA.

The PPI network analysis demonstrated a highly interconnected cluster primarily associated with immune-cell activation, chemokine/cytokine signaling, and T-cell/B- cell receptor pathways. Recent studies have shown that CXCL 13, a B-cell attracting chemokine, has been increased in RA and correlates with both synovial lymphoid architecture and disease severity [29]. Network analysis revealed STAT1 and LCK as major hub genes, which act as key kinases in cytokine and T-cell signaling pathways, further supporting the importance of JAK/STAT and T-cell kinase pathways in RA [30], [31]. Genes associated with metabolism and cell cycle (e.g., involving PPAR- γ , AMPK, CDK1) were identified by enrichment analysis, supporting the concept of RA as not only an immune driven but also a metabolic dysregulation disease [32], [33]. The selected hub genes showed significant dysregulation in independent expression dataset, increasing in their association with RA.

The identification of hub genes- CXCL9, CXCL13, CD27, CD3D and IL32 indicates interconnected mechanisms of immune cell recruitment, activation and effector function. CXCL9 and CXCL13 act as key mediators of T and B Cell infiltration and ectopic lymphoid like structures within synovium, associated with severe disease and worsened clinical outcomes [29], [34]. CD27 and CD3D reflect the fundamental role of T-cell co-stimulation and antigen receptor signaling in maintaining synovial inflammation. IL32, a potent cytokine inducer including TNF- α / IL-6, may amplify local inflammatory cascades and enhance tissue erosion [35]. Together, these genetic insights are consistent with the current understanding of RA pathogenesis as a convergence of autoimmunity, chronic inflammation, and tissue destruction [36]. In addition, alteration in metabolic pathways such as down regulated PPAR- γ / AMPK pathways indicates that synovial fibroblasts and immune cells undergo maladaptive metabolic reprogramming which may sustain inflammation and resist therapy [32].

In terms of clinical translation, the identified hub genes represent potential candidates for biomarker development and therapeutic targeting. Specifically, elevated CXCL13 has been suggested as a prognostic biomarker for radiographic progression [37]. Identification of kinases STAT1, LCK and ITK support the potential for targeted small-molecule or biologic therapy in specific RA patient groups. The integrated bioinformatics approach applied here, which combines multiple datasets and analytical methods, enhances biomarker discovery by reducing false positives and focusing on more reliable candidate genes.

Among the identified hub genes, STAT1 and LCK play central key as mediators sustaining synovial inflammation. STAT1, which acts as a key regulator of interferon-regulated inflammatory transcription, is significantly upregulated in RA fibroblasts like synoviocytes and driven by E2F2 transcriptional regulation, causing sustained proinflammatory signaling [38], [39]. Moreover, LCK, an essential regulator of T-cell receptor signaling, is upregulated in RA synovial T-cell subsets, contributing to sustained T-cell activation and effector-cell development in inflamed joints [40], [41]. Together, these findings highlight the convergence of interferon-STAT1 pathways and T-cell kinase networks in sustaining chronic RA synovitis.

V. CONCLUSION

In summary, this integrated bioinformatics analysis identified coordinated immune activation network of hub genes such as CXCL9, CXCL13, CD3D, STAT1 and IL32 which were validated in independent datasets and enriched for immune, cytokine, chemokine, metabolic and cell-cycle pathways. The present result expands the understanding of RA molecular mechanisms and provides a strong foundation for biomarker development and precision-medicine strategies in RA. Subsequent research should focus on converting these assays into functional assays, diagnostic platforms and drug development.

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